

THE ESSENCE OF THE PREPARATION OF MIDDLE SYLLABLE CADS ON THE BASIS OF AN INTEGRATIVE APPROACH

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Annotation This article presents the basic principles of the theory, the basics and the objects of their unification and the research work carried out by scientists of the Republic on their integration in education, science and production integration.

Аннотация В данной статье представлены основные принципы теории, основы и объекты их объединения, а также исследовательская работа, проводимая учеными республики по их интеграции в сфере образования, науки и производственной интеграции.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada ta'lim, fan va ishlab chiqarish integratsiyasida zamonaviy o'rta bog'in kadrlarni tayyorlash nazariyaning asosiy tamoyillarini, asoslari va ularni birlashtirish o'bektlari hamda ta'limda integratsiyasi bo'yicha respublikamiz olimlari tomonidan olib borilgan tadqiqot ishlari keltirilgan.

Keywords: diagnosis of professional education, integration, motivation, technology, information technology, pedagogical criteria (corporate, didactic) - pedagogical and techno-management base

The system of professional education in Uzbekistan is being coordinated with the needs of the society, which is moving to a new stage of development – the informative stage. In the process of large-scale reforms carried out in the Republic, it is important to form a network of completely new professional educational institutions training middle-tier personnel of innovative technological processes introduced into the sectors of the economy, new technological jobs created in the fields of entrepreneurship, small business.

The concept of integration is very widely used and considered in various aspects under development. Literally translated from Latin "integratio" - restoration, fill, "ration" complete, complete. Consequently, integration is "a whole, any merging into the unity of the elements means restoring some kind of unity". Integration - this is the convergence of disciplines that occur together with differentiation processes and inter-disciplinary at a qualitatively new stage of the communication process and education being a high form of communication implementation, a new whole block, knowledge contributes to the creation of the alloy. Who create the foundations of the worldview, accompanies a person all his life.

The concept of "integration" was explained by Spencer as early as the 18th century. Integral learning is a learning theory holistic lessons that help students side motion description contacts on training programs. This higher education concept from the "integrated curriculum" movement of primary and secondary schools stand out. Integrated research typically focuses on separated topics includes unification so that students are more meaningful and authentic can have an understanding. [1].

There is currently a growing integration of education to produce a complete and clear picture of being. This tradition is forming the basis of the modern concept of Education. It follows from this that the integration of academic disciplines is now observed in both theoretical and practical educational processes. The organization of the educational process through the integration of theory and practice sets the stage for students to look at the events and phenomena taking place in society, the upcoming operational factors and technologies applied in them from the positions of several disciplines, to present them more fully and clearly.

Today, new enterprises, factories and institutions are being built and put into operation and social infrastructure is being developed in all regions of the Republic. All this is increasing the demand for qualified specialists, the development of each industry, the success of projects is directly related to mature personnel.

In the integration of education, science and production, the basic principles of the theory of the training of modern secondary garden personnel can be applied in professional education as follows:

- the functioning of interdisciplinary communication as a method of educational integration and integral formation of the student;
- generalized structural units of knowledge unification serve as complex defects, the structural elements of which differ (interdisciplinary concepts, analysis of concepts, basic ideas, controversial facts);
- development of a classification of interdisciplinary contacts and research of their types (informational, operational, organizational and methodological);
- development of methodological technology for the creation of comprehensive didactic systems aimed at studying complex educational shortcomings that reflect current problems of our time;
- description of the comprehensive forms of the educational enterprise (complex training, complex excursions, complex lecture, assignment, test);
- to prove that interpersonal communication affects the formation of information organization, interdisciplinary skills, broad cognitive interests of students, etc. [2].

The principle of conformity implies the order and consistency of all elements in the system, the logic of the process of forming professional skills, is carried out through a sequence of actions in the structure of the system. In the process of theoretical research can work on the principles identified. The continuity principle provides the basis for the functional stability of the system.

Bringing integrated research to teachers with meaning to their practice to help in the introduction, researchers found that the five basic principles of quality interdisciplinary education are emphasized the aspect: it composes topics that are worth teaching in an interdisciplinary way, disciplinary tools that allow students to understand such topics determines. Effectively unites subjects, combining the sequence of learning experiences with its own includes and evaluates student interdisciplinary work. This framework is interdisciplinary built on years of empirical study of research and class practice.

Integration of Education, Science and production helps to combine these objects: combining information on the foundations of scientific, general cultural, psychological, pedagogical, scientific blocks; interdisciplinary connection – the choice of objects of integration in the system of educational sciences; work – a skillful task combining real

knowledge and education, the subject of work using difficult decision conditions; subjective-personal-integration, includes mental factors and processes (mental, speech, motor, etc.).

Motivational technologies ensure the orientation of students to the application of theoretical knowledge in the practical work of the teacher. Pedagogical technologies help to transfer the knowledge and skills acquired by students to new conditions. Management technologies are used to achieve the didactic goal of professional education, that is, the formation of the ability to solve pedagogical problems, the development of methods and skills of professional pedagogical activity in the process of solving pedagogical problems. In each technology, components (components) are allocated that the teacher can use in accordance with the goals of professional education[7]. The procedural components of technologies (targeted, meaningful, organizational, feedback) expand the scope of their application in the professional field. The purpose of this is to determine the content of the stage of professional training; organizational – use forms of Organization of cognitive activity of students; feedback – the choice of forms of feedback, which allows you to observe the formation of pedagogical problem-solving skills.

We will cite the opinions of scientists of the Republic below, who have carried out scientific research on the training of modern Middle garden personnel in the integration of Education, Science and production[6]. D.Himmataliev the content, components, tools and levels of pedagogical and technical information, the integration of pedagogical and mental, theoretical and real information, the teaching and special integration of subjects, the diagnosis of pedagogical criteria (corporate, didactic) of the effectiveness of teacher's professional education for the teaching of interdisciplinary integration – the pedagogical and techno-educational base combines a teaching methodology based on the mutual integration of pedagogical and technical information to improve the quality of training qualified teachers for qualified work as a means of increasing the student's awareness of their qualifications [3].

In the research carried out by R.K.Choriev, an educational methodology was developed based on the information and didactic provision of improving the readiness of future professional education specialists in education and employees in production for professional activities on the basis of a dual system [4].

And by F.GA'afarov, in the process of training specialists in the process of implementing integration aimed at the development of vocational education, the basis for the transition to a dual system is given, in which the essence of general, induction and production is practically agreed with the features of the educational function. [5].

Today, training programs are a necessary integrative process for professional education – training, improved on the basis of a competency approach, for the development of knowledge, skills, experience, competencies, employment in a professional specialty. It is impossible to effectively formulate students' qualifications without the formation of classical theoretical knowledge and practical abilities. In connection with this important principle of educational technology, the integration of doctrine and practice is considered.

In place of the conclusion, qualified specialists are the basis for the development of any society, after all, in the process of implementing promising plans, professional Education, certain professions occupy a special place. Professional education and its components are an important component in the training of professional personnel.

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